

Motivation and Sports Participation of Secondary School Students in Cross River State, Nigeria

F. A. Dan^{1*}, E. A. Odok², N. N. Osaji³, F. A. Akpong⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Faculty of Education

University of Calabar, Calabar – Nigeria.

* Corresponding Author

Email: odokedmondasu@gmail.com

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine motivation and sports participation among secondary school students in Cross River State, Nigeria. The purpose was achieved through the null hypothesis formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. Literature was reviewed according to the variable of the study. The study adopted the Ex-post factor design because of its appropriateness to the work. A stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the six (66) secondary schools and one thousand three hundred and ninety-three (1393) respondents (student) used for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a structured and validated questionnaire titled "Motivation and Students' Sports Participation Questionnaire" (MSSP). The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method. Simple linear regression statistical tools were used for data analysis. The results obtained from the analysis of data revealed that there was a significant positive influence of motivation of students on their participation in sports. Based on these findings it was recommended that sports administrators in schools should ensure that students are adequately motivated continually both intrinsically to sustain their interest and improve their participation in sport.

Keywords: Motivation, participation, secondary school, sports, students.

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Introduction

The prevalent fear ravaging the minds of a majority of the general public is that participation in sports hinders the success of their words, in the entire process of teaching and learning at schools. Power and Woolger (2018) stated that this misconception was based on their assumption that children who participate in sport can never do well at school. They observed that the most common point of attack against organized athletic activities in school is that most people believe that sports have no positive relationship with academics. Some parents or guardians for obvious reasons associated sports with mischievous behaviours and juvenile delinquency.

Sagar and Lavalley (2010), opined that factors that contribute to students' dropout from school emanate from parents and guardians, such as inadequate financial support and bad attitude toward their wards' education. Those emanating from students are violating the school rules and regulations, frustration due to failure to study hard and failing in the examination. According to Broh (2002), participation in sports activities, in general, is associated with an improved higher educational aspiration, increased college attendance, and reduced absenteeism. Francis (2015) opined that the nature of motivation experienced by secondary school students could influence their level of participation in sport. Students who are naturally in love with a particular sport tend to participate actively in that sport and those who do not have the love may not be interested. Students who are rewarded financially or otherwise through sports or have access to sporting facilities could also be motivated to participate actively in sports. As a result, motivation can be considered as an influential factor that determines the level of participation in sports.

Literature Review

According to Godeon (2016), motivation as social support was one of the aspects identified as predictors of participation and non-participation in sport. Some perceived sports from a health benefits perspective for young children and teenage girls in particular. WHO (2010) stated that a clear opposition could be seen between girls wanting to be physically active and at the same time feminine and the strong macho culture of a school and extracurricular sports. One area where the evidence base is strong is the negative impact that school physical education classes have on the participation of young girls. Changing physical education uniforms, providing single-sex classes and offering alternate, non-competitive forms of physical education is one easy, realistic way in which physical education could be changed and which the research suggests would improve long-term participation.

Similarly, Fernandes (2010), stated that the youth sports Trust/Nice girls project "Girls in sports program involved of schools across England to create girls. Friendly forms of physical education and with changing school practices and community attitude results showed changes in the style of teaching in physical education girl-friendly changing room, positive role model for girls in sports, extended and new types of activities relaxed emphasis on physical education kit and an emphasis on rewarding effort as well as achievement significantly common among peers, classmates and school groups and distance competitors. White (2014) found some evidence of relevance to policymakers about why children and adults do or do not participate in sports and physical activity. In his findings, he discovered that motivation is the key play variable, also Hoopwood et al (2015) stated that motivation is just one of the multivariate variables. A qualitative study of participation in physical activity in Australia found similar motivating factors such as fun enjoyment and socializing with friends and similar barriers including time constraints and negative pressure from peers. Khinho (2010) found that significant shifts in the life course have implications for participation in physical activity.

Nichol (2017) studied the influencing factors by sustained motivation in sports. Motivation is a significant influence desiring sporting activity within a sporting context, motivational factors are imperative when an attempt to maintain standard is made. As a result, awareness towards sustainment of a performed motivation has become increasingly investigated in sport, both in participation and competition. Coaches have to adapt to each individual; both the athlete and coach influence each other.

Methods

In this study, the researchers made use of the Ex-post-facto research design which is meant to describe and interpret existing conditions of sports participation of secondary school students. The population of this study comprised 13881 senior secondary school students in public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. The sample for this study was comprised (1383) senior secondary school (SS2) students in Cross River State, Nigeria. The instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. The closed-ended questionnaire was constructed and administered to the respondents to enable them to choose the alternatives that best described their opinions. The questionnaire contained two parts, part 1 is focused on the demographic data of the respondents while part 2 contained data on motivation and sport participation. To determine the reliability of the instrument used for the study, test-retest reliability was conducted on a smaller sample size using independent t-test analysis (t) and the result yielded 75. This shows a high level of reliability.

Results

Hypothesis 1

Motivation does not significantly influence sports participation of secondary school students in Cross River State. A simple linear regression analysis was performed to test the null hypothesis at the .05 level of significance. The result of the analysis presented in table 1 showed that the predictor or independent variable (motivation) significantly influenced the predicted variable (sports participation among secondary school students) in Cross River State. The regression ANOVA revealed that there was a significant positive influence of motivation on sports participation among secondary school students in Cross River State, $F_{(1,1379)} = 192.878, p < .05$.

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis of the influence of motivation on sports participation among secondary school students in Cross River State (N=1381)

R	R ²		Adj.R ²	SE		
350	.123		.122	3.561		
Source	SS	Df	SS	F-ratio	p	
Regression	2446.598	1	2446.598	192.878	.000	
Residual	17492.166	1379	12.685			
Total	19938.765	1380				

Discussion

The finding obtained from the analysis and testing of the hypothesis reveals that the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there is a significant positive influence of motivation on secondary school student's participation in Cross River State. The finding of this study further supported the finding of Godeon (2016) which reported that motivation as social support was one of the aspects identified as predictors of participation and non-participation in sports. Some perceived sports from a health benefits perspective for young children and teenage girls in particular. The finding of this study also supported the finding of the World Health Organization (2010) which stated that a clear opposition can be seen between girls wanting to be physically active and at the same time feminine and the strong macho culture of the school and extracurricular sports. One area where the evidence base is strong is the negative impacts that school physical education (PE) classes have on the participation of young girls. Changing uniform providing single-sex classes and offering an alternate, non-competitive forms of physical education are easy.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusion was made: there was a significant positive influence on motivation on secondary school student's participation in sport in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendation is made:

Sports administration in schools should ensure that students are adequately motivated continually both intrinsically and extrinsically to sustain their interest and improve their participation in sports.

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